

Assertive Behavior, Emotion Regulation, and Marital Satisfaction in Husbands During Early Marriage

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Abstract

Marital satisfaction is crucial, particularly for husbands, and it has garnered significant attention among researchers. The focus on marital satisfaction is particularly emphasized during the early stages of marriage, as this period lays the foundation influencing the longevity of the marital union. This study aims to examine the impact of assertive behavior and emotional regulation on marital satisfaction during the initial phases of marriage. The research involves 114 husbands in the early stages of marriage, and data is collected through questionnaires. Multiple regression analysis is employed for data analysis. The findings reveal that there is a 23.1% influence of assertive behavior and emotional regulation on marital satisfaction. The research indicates that emotional regulation holds a stronger influence compared to assertive behavior, as effective emotional regulation assists individuals in navigating challenging situations.

Keywords: *marital satisfaction, assertive behavior, emotional regulation, husbands, early marriage*

INTRODUCTION

The majority of individuals choose to seek partners and establish deeper relationships during adulthood. Marriage becomes one of the desired needs of every human being, with marriage serving as a formal emotional commitment between two people or couples to share physical feelings, share various tasks, and manage economic resources (Indriani, 2014). Many events occur, especially in the first years of marriage, and every couple must be able to face various problems because the initial phase of marriage is a period highly vulnerable to dissolution (Olson, DeFrain & Skogrand, 2019).

Newly married couples, commonly referred to as newly-weds, face challenges during the initial period of marriage as it is a time when couples strive to achieve happiness and life stability between husband and wife who together must meet life's demands while establishing marital foundations that are compatible with their partnership (Anjani & Suryanto, 2006). Previous research conducted by Schramm, Marshall, Harris, and Lee (2005) stated that the initial phase of marriage years becomes crucial because it is during this phase that couples can build a foundation that will direct the course of their marriage, potentially resulting in high marital satisfaction in the years to come.

Based on Indonesian statistical data, there were 447,743 divorce cases in 2021, showing an increase of 53.50% compared to divorce rates in 2020 (Annur, 2022). In the same year, there were 279,205 divorce cases stemming from disputes and conflicts (Annur, 2022). This data indicates that many couples experience marital dissatisfaction, resulting in conflicts and disputes. These findings align with the predictions of Gottman & Levenson (2002), who stated that marital dissatisfaction can lead to relationship breakdown and ultimately divorce, highlighting the necessity of achieving satisfaction in marital relationships

Couples need time and experience to understand their respective roles in marriage. The first 0-5 years of marriage represent a critical period for the marriage as there is still limited experience between partners (Dewi & Sudhana, 2013). According to Duvall and Miller (in Wulan & Chotimah, 2017), marital satisfaction peaks during the initial phase of marriage. This occurs because during the first five years of marriage, couples tend to encounter more problems compared to other marriage durations (Zaheri, Dolatian, Shariati, Simbar, Ebadi, & Azghadi, 2016).

Couples who maintain mutual care will create marital satisfaction, but if there is dissatisfaction in marriage, it will lead to negative impacts ranging from arguments to potential divorce. Research conducted by Rozalinda & Nurhasanah (2014) revealed that not all married couples can create a marriage that is happy, peaceful, tranquil, harmonious, and lasting. Many couples who do not experience satisfaction in their marriage choose to end it through divorce (Harahap & Lestari, 2018).

Maintaining a lasting marriage life is the hope of every married couple and serves as an indicator of successful household management. One of the key role holders in marriage is the husband, who acts as the captain and has rights and duties as explained by Lestary (2015), which include roles as decision-maker, financial manager, and the person responsible for nurturing. According to Olson and Fower (1989), factors such as communication, leisure time management, religious views, problem-solving, financial management, sexual orientation, relationships with family and friends, roles and child-rearing, personality issues, roles and duties, and realistic views all contribute to assessing marital satisfaction. Couples need to be able to communicate their desires effectively, but this must also be accompanied by responsibility, to form a strong marital relationship.

Norgren et al. (in Villa & Del Prette, 2013) concluded that openness and healthy communication have a positive relationship with satisfaction levels in long-lasting marriages. This openness can also be referred to as assertive behavior. Assertive behavior is necessary as support for marital satisfaction because couples with good levels of assertiveness can effectively communicate their problems, opinions, and ideas clearly to their partners, which in turn can reduce the potential for arguments in household relationships (Ramadhani & Afiatin, 2020).

Assertive behavior plays a role in difficulties in emotion regulation (Anto, 2023), where assertiveness mediates maladaptive patterns by changing individual cognitive processes so that they can reinterpret situations to reduce the effects of emotional dysregulation. The ability to regulate emotions makes individuals more capable of accepting and valuing themselves (Kurniasih & Pratisi, 2013). Household problems can cause husbands to experience pressure, and if individuals facing crisis are unable to cope with the situation, they may experience emotional instability (Swinson, 2017). Emotion regulation refers to ways of influencing experienced

emotions, when to feel them, and how to experience and express these emotions (Gross, 1998). Assertive behavior plays a role in difficulties in emotion regulation (Anto, 2023), where assertiveness mediates maladaptive patterns by changing individual cognitive processes so that they can reinterpret situations to reduce the effects of emotional dysregulation. The ability to regulate emotions makes individuals more capable of accepting and valuing themselves (Kurniasih & Pratisi, 2013).

Husbands who can manage their emotions have good levels of marital satisfaction. This aligns with research findings by Rifayanti & Diana (2019), which showed that in the context of marriage, couples need to have good conflict resolution styles, marital communication abilities, and emotional regulation capabilities. This is also supported by research conducted by Amalia (in Islamy & Ningsih, 2019) in Semarang with married couples working as factory employees, showing that there is a relationship between assertive behavior and marital satisfaction. This means that the higher the assertive behavior of couples, the higher their marital satisfaction.

Research on emotion regulation and marital satisfaction conducted by Ben-Naim, Hirschberger, Ein-Dor, and Mikulincer (2013) on married couples found that emotion regulation is crucial in building relationships. Married individuals are expected not only to rely on communication but also to understand proper regulation when facing problems. Emotion regulation will help individuals emerge from unfavorable situations. Another study conducted by Wulan and Chotimah (2017) on married couples found that there is a positive influence between emotion regulation and marital satisfaction in married couples, meaning that the better an individual's ability to regulate their emotions, the higher their satisfaction with their marriage.

Based on the above description, it can be seen that assertive behavior and emotion regulation play important roles in achieving marital satisfaction, thus researchers are interested in understanding the influence of assertive behavior and emotion regulation on marital satisfaction in early marriage. The purpose of this study is to determine whether there is an influence of assertive behavior and emotion regulation on marital satisfaction in early marriage.

RESEARCH METHOD

This research involved 114 husbands reached through online questionnaires. Participants were male. The sampling technique was determined using non-probability sampling, specifically purposive sampling, with predetermined criteria: male gender, married status, having children, and residing within the territory of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia.

Marital satisfaction was measured using a scale translated and adapted from Fowers and Olson (1993) with ten dimensional scales: personality issues, communication, conflict resolution, financial management, leisure activities, sexual relationship, children and parenting, family and friends, equalitarian roles, and religious orientation. An example item is "I am not happy with my communication with my spouse and feel my spouse doesn't understand me." Response options ranged from 1-5 with responses from strongly agree to strongly disagree. This scale initially had 15 items. After calculating discrimination power, two items were eliminated, leaving 12 remaining items, with a reliability value of 0.868.

Assertive behavior was measured using a scale translated and adapted from Alberti and Emmons (2002) using aspects of acting according to one's own desires, honest and comfortable expression of feelings, self-defense ability, ability to express opinions, and not disregarding others' rights. An example item from this scale is "I often give in to my partner." Response options ranged from 1-5 with responses from strongly agree to strongly disagree. This scale initially had 30 items. After calculating discrimination power, 18 items were eliminated, leaving 12 remaining items, with a reliability value of 0.832.

Emotion regulation was measured using a scale translated and adapted from Gross and John (2002), using aspects of cognitive reappraisal and expressive suppression. An example item from this scale is "I control my emotions by not expressing them." Response options ranged from 1-5 with responses from strongly agree to strongly disagree. This scale initially had 10 items, and after calculating discrimination power, no items were eliminated. The reliability value of the emotion regulation scale was 0.850.

This research used multiple linear regression analysis with SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Science) version 23.0 for windows. Meanwhile, other descriptive data are presented using percentage calculations.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Findings related to demographic data can be seen in Table 1. The data presented in Table 1 contains information about subjects' age, marriage duration, and number of children. Based on the data in Table 1, it can be determined that the problematic topics causing concern among husbands are financial issues, children, family, friends, busy schedules and long-distance relationships, as well as problems related to possessiveness, domestic violence, and infidelity. Communication problems become issues that will negatively impact marriage continuity; being assertive is necessary as support for marital satisfaction because couples with good levels of assertiveness can effectively communicate their problems, opinions, and ideas clearly to their partners, which in turn can reduce the potential for arguments in household relationships (Ramadhani & Afiatin, 2020).

Tab1e. 1. Description of Demographic Data

Description	Number	Percentage
Age		
20-25 years	27	23.7%
26-40 years	84	73.7%
≥41 years	3	2.6%
Marriage Duration		
0-1 year	10	8.8%
2 years	26	22.8%
3 years	27	23.7%
4 years	21	18.4%
5 years	30	26.3%
Number of Children		

1 child	68	59.6%
2 children	31	27.2%
3 children	8	7%
≥4 children	7	6.1%
Problem Topics		
Financial	37	32.4%
Communication	45	39.4%
Children, Family, and Friends	15	13.1%
Busy and Long-distance Relationships	9	7.9%
Others (Possessiveness, Domestic Violence, Infidelity)	8	7.0%

Table 2. Regression Test Results of Assertive Behavior and Emotion Regulation on Marital Satisfaction

<i>F</i>	<i>sig.</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>R Square</i>
16.637	0.000	≤ 0.05	0.231

Tabel 3. Regression Coefficients of Assertive Behavior and Emotion Regulation on Marital Satisfaction

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	24.35	3.710		6.56	0.000
Assertive Behavior	-0.167	0.082	-0.207	-2.042	0.043
Emotion Regulation	0.473	0.084	0.566	5.601	0.000

Based on Table 2, an F-value of 16.637 and significance coefficient of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$) were obtained, indicating a significant influence of assertive behavior and emotion regulation on marital satisfaction among husbands in early marriage. Additionally, the R Square value of 0.231 shows that emotion regulation and assertive behavior together influence marital satisfaction by 23.1%.

Furthermore, Table 3 shows a significance coefficient for the emotion regulation variable of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$) with $\beta = 0.566$ or 56.6% influence. For the assertive behavior variable, the significance coefficient is 0.043 ($p < 0.05$) with $\beta = -0.207$ or 20.7% influence. This indicates that both variables significantly influence marital satisfaction in husbands during early marriage, however, when analyzed individually, the assertive behavior variable shows no influence on marital satisfaction in husbands during early marriage.

This research demonstrates that emotion regulation is a strong predictor. This aligns with previous research stating that individuals with good emotion regulation can maintain emotional stability even under pressure (Reivich & Shatte, 2002). This affects decision-making by husbands in the household, creating harmonious relationships. Another study by Wulan and Chotimah (2017) on married couples found a positive influence between emotion regulation and marital satisfaction, meaning better emotional regulation ability correlates with higher marital satisfaction.

Assertive behavior also plays a role in marital satisfaction in this study. This is supported by Laswell and Lobsenz (in Duvall & Miller, 1985), who state that marital satisfaction depends on the extent of interaction or communication between partners and how well each partner's expectations can be identified. This is further supported by Amalia's (2016) research showing an influence between assertive behavior and marital satisfaction levels.

Similar results were found in Kumaladewi and Uyun's (2010) research, which discovered a positive relationship between assertive behavior and marital satisfaction levels in husbands. In other words, higher levels of assertive behavior correlate with higher levels of marital satisfaction in husbands. Assertive behavior can improve marriage relationship quality by making it more open and honest, as partners have the right and freedom to express themselves (Villa & del Prette, 2013). Marital satisfaction is crucial for couples because dissatisfaction can lead to relationship breakdown and ultimately divorce, emphasizing the need for satisfaction in marital relationships (Gottman & Levenson, 2002).

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of this study, it can be concluded that assertive behavior and emotion regulation together influence marital satisfaction in husbands during early marriage. It was found that emotion regulation can reduce the frequency of husband's arguments, while assertive behavior can increase the frequency of arguments which then affects satisfaction in marriage.

For future researchers, it is recommended to consider other variables that have not been measured in this study. Additionally, it is suggested that future researchers use open-ended questions in questionnaires, to complement data from closed-ended questions, to reveal more factual information about marital satisfaction.

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